

Host-guest complexes : spectroscopic and thermodynamic studies of cyclodextrins-dyes

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The interactions between hosts α - and β -cyclodextrins and guests phenolphthalein, acridine, 4-(*p*-*N,N*-dimethyl-*N*-amyl)-styrylpyridinium bromide, azurene-A, azurene-B and azurene-C have been studied spectroscopically. Spectroscopic and thermodynamic parameters indicate that the interaction between the cyclodextrins and the above dyes is weak. β -Cyclodextrin forms relatively stronger complexes with the above dyes. In most of the cases the complexation is enthalpy-controlled rather than entropy-controlled.

Recently much attention has been focussed on cyclodextrin as a model for enzymatic process¹⁻⁴. Cyclodextrin cavities can bind apolar/ionic molecules of suitable size to form 'host-guest' complexes⁵. The interaction between cyclodextrin and neutral organic molecule (of appropriate size) is assumed to be due to hydrophobic interaction and/or hydrogen bonding, van der Waals forces, whereas the ion-dipole interaction is responsible for the interaction between ionic guest species and neutral host.

As there is no regular bond formation between the host and guest, the substrate entrapment in cyclodextrin is a dynamic process and there is an exchange between bound and free cyclodextrin and substrate. So, as the interaction between the cyclodextrins and substrate is weak, it is not easy to obtain reliable equilibrium constant and other thermodynamic parameters for the formation of host-guest complexes and the results reported from various laboratories for the same complex vary considerably^{3,4}. For more comprehensive understanding of the nature of the non-covalent interaction operating between host cyclodextrin and guest molecules, a good deal of efforts is required to investigate complexation thermodynamics of several types of guest molecules with cyclodextrins⁶⁻⁹. For developing and testing any theory/model, one requires reliable spectroscopic and thermodynamic data. However, when one critically examines the data reported from different laboratories the divergence seems to be too much^{1,3,4}. Therefore, it was thought worthwhile to carry out a systematic investigation to obtain reliable spectroscopic and thermodynamic data of host-guest complexes so that one can try to infer the nature of interaction between the host and guest.

In the present investigations the hosts are α -cyclodextrin and β -cyclodextrin. The dyes used are known to be good hydrophobic probes and exhibit absorption spectra in the

visible region and they are molecules with large conjugation, with different substitution – azurene-A, azurene-B and azurene-C, acridine, phenolphthalein and 4-(*p*-*N,N*-dimethyl-*N*-amyl)styrylpyridinium bromide (APB).

Results and Discussion

Phenolphthalein- β -cyclodextrin complex :

Phenolphthalein in alkaline media has absorption maxima at 285 ± 1 ($\epsilon = 10819 \pm 294$), 375 ($\epsilon = 5981 \pm 104$) and 553 ± 1 nm ($\epsilon = 33354 \pm 105$ dm³ mol⁻¹ cm⁻¹). The 553 nm band is the most intense band. The intensities of phenolphthalein bands depend on pH of the medium. Phenolphthalein is colourless at pH ~ 8 and lower. As pH of the solution is increased from 9.43 to 10.53 the molar extinction coefficient of phenolphthalein increases from 25757 to 33354 ± 105 dm³ mol⁻¹ cm⁻¹. Our results go in parallel with those of earlier workers². On further increase in pH of the medium, the molar extinction coefficient starts decreasing and the intensity of the bands can be attributed to the formation of carbinol. At higher pH, the pink colour of phenolphthalein slowly fades, producing different structures. All the colour changes are reversible (with the change in pH of the solution). As the intensity of phenolphthalein at 10.53 pH is maximum and constant, this pH was maintained throughout the present investigations (by using 4×10^{-3} M sodium carbonated solution). As the temperature of phenolphthalein solution is increased from 298 to 318 K, the molar extinction coefficient of phenolphthalein is slightly decreased (from 33354 to 31032) and at the same time the half-band width is slightly increased from 1607 to 1692 cm⁻¹. The slight decrease in the intensity of phenolphthalein band with the increase in temperature may partly be due to the increase in volume of the solution (decrease in concentration of the solution) and partly to the transformation to different structure and partly due to the change in

shape/increase in half-width of the band. In the absence of more quantitative data, we are not in a position to calculate or predict the contributions of each of the above plausible processes.

The absorption spectra of phenolphthalein- β -cyclodextrin and their complexes of various concentrations of β -cyclodextrin at 10.53 pH are shown in Fig. 1. It can be seen

Fig. 1. Absorption spectra of phenolphthalein with various concentration of β -cyclodextrin : Concentration of β -CD = (1) 0, (2) 1.2×10^{-4} , (3) 2.1×10^{-4} , (4) 3.1×10^{-4} , (5) 4.1×10^{-4} M; Temp. = 298 K, pH = 10.53, concn. of phenolphthalein = 5.5×10^{-5} M.

that with the addition of β -cyclodextrin, the absorbances of phenolphthalein bands decrease and the decrease continues with the further addition of β -cyclodextrin. This decrease in absorbance of phenolphthalein is due to the inclusion of some of the phenolphthalein molecules into the β -cyclodextrin cavity³. Here it may be noted that Izat *et al.*⁹ reported that cyclodextrin undergoes hydrolysis at and above pH 12; however, we did not find any change in the absorbance of cyclodextrin at 10.53 pH. So from this we can

infer that probably at 10.53 pH, the ionization of cyclodextrin does not take place or the amount of cyclodextrin ionized is negligible. With the addition of β -cyclodextrin, not only the absorbance at 553 nm decreases but also a new band, due to the host-guest complex, appears at 245 ± 1 nm and the intensity of this band increases with the addition of cyclodextrin. A sharp isosbestic point is observed at 271 nm with $\epsilon_{\text{iso}} = 11423 \pm 155 \text{ dm}^3 \text{ mol}^{-1} \text{ cm}^{-1}$. The presence of an isosbestic point and the appearance of a new band (CT band) and the reversible intensity changes of the new as well as of phenolphthalein bands clearly indicate that phenolphthalein 'interacts' with cyclodextrin and forms a reversible host-guest complex. The absorbance of the new band is constant during the course of investigation (≈ 4 h) and this indicates that the complex formed is stable. The absorption maximum of phenolphthalein slightly shifts to higher wavelength. However, as the absorption of CT band due to the complex (i.e. host-guest complex) was very low, it was not possible to study the effect of variation of concentration of β -cyclodextrin on λ_{CT} . The stoichiometry of the complex was determined using Job's¹² and continuous variation methods and it was found to be 1 : 1. The equilibrium constant and other thermodynamic parameters of the β -cyclodextrin-phenolphthalein complex were calculated and are summarized in Table 1. The charge transfer band appeared at 245 nm and the equilibrium constant, calculated using B-H equation, was $11934 \pm 2143 \text{ dm}^3 \text{ mol}^{-1}$ and $\epsilon_{\text{CT}} = 5640 \pm 155 \text{ dm}^3 \text{ mol}^{-1} \text{ cm}^{-1}$. Here it may be noted that frequency of charge transfer absorption band is primary data which is reasonably certain, whereas the equilibrium constant, molar extinction coefficient, enthalpy and entropy

Table 1. Spectroscopic and thermodynamic parameters of host-guest complexes*

Host : β -Cyclodextrin										
Guest	λ_{com}^a nm	ϵ_{com}^a $\text{dm}^3 \text{ mol}^{-1} \text{ cm}^{-1}$	λ_{com}^a nm	ϵ_{iso}^a $\text{dm}^3 \text{ mol}^{-1}$	K_{298} $\text{dm}^3 \text{ mol}^{-1}$	K_{303} $\text{dm}^3 \text{ mol}^{-1}$	K_{308} $\text{dm}^3 \text{ mol}^{-1}$	$-\Delta H^\circ$ kJ mol^{-1}	$-\Delta G^\circ$ kJ mol^{-1}	$-\Delta S^\circ$ J mol^{-1}
Phenolphthalein	245	5640 ± 155 (5489)	271	11423 ± 124	11934 ± 213 (11871) 11262 ^b	10715 (10295) 10325 ^b	9550 (9817) 9332 ^b	6.61 (6.65)	10.08 (10.03)	-0.011 (-0.011)
Acridine	272 (404)	1166 ± 67	382	2272 ± 43	310 ± 7 (332)	214 (227)	162 (179)	24.1 (23.44)	6.17 (6.24)	0.060 (0.058)
APB	472	3125 ± 132	430	21969 ± 108	1206 ± 38 (926)	1094 (767)	867 (660)	12.47 (11.63)	7.34 (7.63)	0.017 (0.013)
Azurene-A	639	7462 ± 95	611	27912 ± 137	1203 ± 12 (1297)	1196 (1224)	1030 (1096)	5.81 (5.80)	7.60 (7.70)	-0.0061 (-0.0063)
Azurene-B	658	5882 ± 142	629	29447 ± 117	1155 ± 18 (1173)	1064 (1097)	963 (987)	6.6 (6.6)	7.58 (7.60)	-0.003 (-0.0031)
Azurene-C	622	3125 ± 97	601	30803 ± 177	1862 ± 13 (1880)	1717 (1732)	1584 (1602)	5.83 (5.78)	8.10 (8.11)	-0.0076 (-0.0078)

*Values in parenthesis refer to those obtained by using Nagakura's equation (Ref. 11)^aError limit : ± 1 nm. ^bRef. 3.

changes are secondary data – derived data, which have higher uncertainties. Any of the secondary data can be used for a comparison with theory only with great caution. In B-H modified B-H equations¹⁰, the molar extinction coefficient and the equilibrium constant K are obtained by the separation of $K\varepsilon$, and the uncertainties in these values are very high. So, for obtaining the enthalpy, assuming that ε is practically independent (i.e. in applying vant Hoff equation) of temperature, $\log K\varepsilon$ is plotted against $1/T$.

The equilibrium constant K , for β -cyclodextrin-phenolphthalein is quite large, but from the enthalpy, ΔH° , and free energy, ΔG° , values, the host-guest complex seems to be weak. The entropy, ΔS° , is small and negative and this indicates that the system is enthalpy-controlled.

Phenolphthalein- α -cyclodextrin complex :

On the addition of α -cyclodextrin the absorption of phenolphthalein at 553 nm decreases and at the same time a new band at 242 nm appears. The intensity of this band increases with the addition of α -cyclodextrin. A sharp isosbestic point was observed at 271 nm ($\varepsilon_{\text{iso}} = 11482 \text{ dm}^3 \text{ mol}^{-1} \text{ cm}^{-1}$). The appearance of the isosbestic point and the linear decrease in the absorbance of 553 nm band with the increase in concentration of α -cyclodextrin, clearly indicate the presence of a complex formed due to the interaction between phenolphthalein and α -cyclodextrin. Absorbance of the new band (242 nm) remained constant during the course of investigation (~4 h) and this indicates that the complex is quite stable. Equilibrium constants for α -cyclodextrin-phenolphthalein complex formation are given in Table 2.

Fig. 2 shows the decrease in absorption of phenolphthalein (of the same concentration) with the addition of α - and β -cyclodextrins. From the spectra it is evident that when cyclodextrins (α - and β -) of the same concentrations were added to a fixed concentration of phenolphthalein, the de-

Fig. 2. Comparison of spectra of α - and β -CD of same concentration with a constant concentration of phenolphthalein, temp. = 298 K, pH = 10.53; concn. of phenolphthalein = $2.2 \times 10^{-5} \text{ M}$, concn. of CD = (3.1, 4.1 and 5.1) $\times 10^{-4} \text{ M}$.

crease in absorbance of phenolphthalein was much more, when β -cyclodextrin is added, indicating that more phenolphthalein molecules are entrapped in β -cyclodextrin. The charge transfer energy of α -cyclodextrin complex is slightly higher than that of β -cyclodextrin complex. In addition, the equilibrium constant for α -cyclodextrin-phenolphthalein at 298 K is $387 \pm 32 \text{ dm}^3 \text{ mol}^{-1}$, whereas for the β -cyclodextrin, it is $11934 \pm 213 \text{ dm}^3 \text{ mol}^{-1}$. Similarly, for α -cyclodextrin-phenolphthalein, ΔG° is 6.41 kJ mol^{-1} , which is slightly lower than that of β -cyclodextrin-phenolphthalein ($10.08 \text{ kJ mol}^{-1}$). α -Cyclodextrin cavity is smaller (4.7–5.1 Å) than that of β -cyclodextrin (6.0–6.4 Å). As the forces responsible for the interaction between host-guest system are mainly van der Waals and/or hydrophobic interaction, the size of the host seems to play an important role.

The cavity of β -cyclodextrin is larger compared to that of α -cyclodextrin. The size-fit concept, which predicts the highest complex stabilities for the best size-matched host-guest pairs, may explain the trends of the thermodynamic quantities for complexation of natural cyclodextrins. As the van der Waals forces are critically dependent on the dis-

Table 2. Spectroscopic and thermodynamic parameters of host-guest complexes*

Host : α -Cyclodextrin										
Guest	λ_{com}^a nm	ε_{com} $\text{dm}^3 \text{ mol}^{-1} \text{ cm}^{-1}$	λ_{iso}^a nm	ε_{iso} $\text{dm}^3 \text{ mol}^{-1} \text{ cm}^{-1}$	K_{298} $\text{dm}^3 \text{ mol}^{-1}$	K_{303} $\text{dm}^3 \text{ mol}^{-1}$	K_{308} $\text{dm}^3 \text{ mol}^{-1}$	$-\Delta H^\circ$ kJ mol^{-1}	$-\Delta G^\circ$ kJ mol^{-1}	$-\Delta S^\circ$ J mol^{-1}
Phenolphthalein	242	5555 ± 114 5540^b	271	11482 ± 124	387 ± 32 (372) 367^b	363 (324)	309 (295)	9.14 (9.14)	6.41 (6.36)	0.0094 (0.0093)
Acridine	404	1769 ± 59	386	2095 ± 59	153 ± 3 (178)	147 (170)	144 (163)	2.49 (3.32)	5.40 (5.57)	-0.0097 (-0.0076)
APB	492	4761 ± 83	432	24604 ± 117	752 ± 12 (674)	617 (580)	497 (427)	16.63 (15.78)	7.01 (7.13)	0.032 (0.029)

*Values in parenthesis refer to those obtained by using Nagakura's equation (Ref. 11).^aError Limit : $\pm 1 \text{ nm}$. ^bRef. 3.

tance of separation, one can expect that the forces induced upon complexation of relatively rigid guests (compared to straight-chain guests) with β -cyclodextrin will be larger to that of α -cyclodextrin complex. In addition, the release of water molecules from the cyclodextrin cavity and its close proximity to the bulk water and the pre-arrangement of nearby water molecules may play an important role in the overall complexation of thermodynamics. Linert *et al.*¹³ opined that the β -cyclodextrin cavity is hydrophobic but that of the α -cyclodextrin cavity cannot clearly be placed in this category due to which the interaction with β -cyclodextrin is slightly stronger. The other plausible explanation is the contribution of hydrogen bonding of the guest molecule to the complexation thermodynamics of cyclodextrin. However, with the limited experimental data, we are not in a position to generalise these effects on complexation. On the basis of spectroscopic and thermodynamic parameters, one is tempted to infer that phenolphthalein probably fits more properly in β -cyclodextrin cavity compared to α -cyclodextrin.

Acridine- β -cyclodextrin complex :

Acridine has three absorption bands at 338 ($\epsilon = 5736 \pm 53$), 347 ($\epsilon = 6492 \pm 38$) and 355 nm ($\epsilon = 10395 \pm 75 \text{ dm}^3 \text{ mol}^{-1} \text{ cm}^{-1}$). In addition, a shoulder appears at $\approx 382 \pm 3$ nm ($\epsilon = 2466 \pm 83 \text{ dm}^3 \text{ mol}^{-1} \text{ cm}^{-1}$) and these values compare well with the literature data¹⁴. The band at 355 nm can be attributed to the π - π^* transition. With the increase in temperature (from 298 to 308 K), the molar extinction coefficients of 355 nm band decreases from 10395 to 9976 $\text{dm}^3 \text{ mol}^{-1} \text{ cm}^{-1}$ whereas the half-width of the band increases from 1984 to 2114 cm^{-1} . It is quite interesting to note that the decrease in molar extinction coefficient is $\approx 2\%$ (for 5° change in temperature) and the increase in half-width is $\approx 1.9\%$. So on the basis of these data, we are tempted to infer that the apparent decrease in absorbance of acridine can be due to the change in band shape, i.e. increase in band half-width.

With the addition of β -cyclodextrin, the absorbance of acridine, e.g. absorbance of 355 nm band decreases and this decrease depends on the amount of β -cyclodextrin added. In addition, with the addition of β -cyclodextrin, the absorbance of acridine above 382 nm increases and this increase depends on the concentration of β -cyclodextrin added. The band maxima in 382–500 nm region was found to be ≈ 404 nm and this can be attributed to host-guest complex. The absorption of this new band is temperature-dependent and is reversible with the temperature. An isosbestic point at 382 nm is observed. The presence of an isosbestic point and the reversible absorbance of the band at 382–500 nm

indicate that acridine and β -cyclodextrin interact with each other and form a reversible 'host-guest' complex. Eventhough there is increase in the absorbance in 382–500 nm region, the increase in absorbance (due to the complex formation) is not much and this indicates that the concentration of the complex (molar extinction coefficient) is very low, which may be due to the weak interaction between the host and the guest. In addition, from the differential spectra, a new band was located at 272 nm ($\epsilon = 1666 \text{ dm}^3 \text{ mol}^{-1} \text{ cm}^{-1}$). Here it may be mentioned that even though acridine is classified as a π -electron deficient heterocycle^{15,16}, Kinoshita¹⁶ showed that acridine is an electron donor. In literature one comes across such cases where more than one intermolecular charge transfer transitions are observed¹⁷. The multiplicity of the bands might have been arisen from electron donation from more than one energy levels of the donor to the acceptor (of more than on energy levels of the acceptor). It is also possible that the double charge transfer bands are observed due to the removal of degeneracy of the energy level (as in the case of methylbenzene by substitution). It is plausible that the relative orientation of donor/host and guest in an interaction can give rise to double bands. In the absence of any theoretical values of energy of the highest/penultimate orbital and lowest unoccupied molecular orbital of the acceptor molecule, it is not possible to pinpoint the origin of these multiple bands.

The equilibrium constants of host-guest complex formation, were determined at 25, 30 and 35° and these values are given in Table 1. The enthalpy of complex formation is $\sim 24 \text{ kJ mol}^{-1}$ and the entropy of the complex is $-0.060 \text{ J mol}^{-1}$. So, it appears that the host-guest system is enthalpy-controlled rather than entropy-controlled. It was mentioned earlier that acridine can act like a π -donor and β -cyclodextrin is a host. So the interaction between the host and the guest cannot be specific and the interaction can be of van der Waals type.

Acridine- α -cyclodextrin complex :

The absorbance of acridine at λ_{max} (355 nm) decreases with the addition of α -cyclodextrin. In addition, there is an increase in absorbance above 380 nm, and the band maxima was found to be at 404 nm. Further, an isosbestic point was obtained at ~ 386 nm ($\epsilon_{\text{iso}} = 2095 \pm 59 \text{ dm}^3 \text{ mol}^{-1} \text{ cm}^{-1}$) indicating that the acridine and α -cyclodextrin interact to form 'host-guest' complex.

The equilibrium constants were determined at 25, 30 and 35°. The equilibrium constant value is not very high and the molar extinction coefficient is very low. The enthalpy of complex formation is 24.9 kJ mol^{-1} and the entropy is $-0.0097 \text{ J mol}^{-1}$. So it appears that the complex

formation is enthalpy-controlled rather than entropy-controlled and the interaction is very weak–van der Waals type.

From the spectroscopic and thermodynamic parameters of β -cyclodextrin-acridine and α -cyclodextrin-acridine complexes it is evident that the interaction between β -cyclodextrin and acridine is stronger compared to that of α -cyclodextrin and acridine.

4(p-N,N-Dimethyl-N-amyl)styrylpyridinium bromide (APB) – β -cyclodextrin complex :

The electronic absorption spectra of 4-(*p-N,N*-dimethyl-*N*-amyl)styrylpyridinium bromide consist of two peaks at 267 ($\epsilon = 8390 \pm 95$) and 453 nm ($\epsilon = 22537 \pm 120 \text{ dm}^3 \text{ mol}^{-1} \text{ cm}^{-1}$) (lit.^{19b} 450 nm). The intensities of these bands did not change with time and this indicates that the dye is quite stable. The data on temperature variation studies indicate that the molar extinction coefficients of both the bands slightly decrease (from 22537 and 8390 $\text{dm}^3 \text{ mol}^{-1} \text{ cm}^{-1}$ to 22375 and 8020 $\text{dm}^3 \text{ mol}^{-1} \text{ cm}^{-1}$, respectively) with the increase in temperature (from 298 to 308 K) and the half-band width of 453 nm band slightly increases from 5897 to 5964 cm^{-1} . However, our attempts to study the effect of temperature on the half-band width of 267 nm band were not successful as the tail of the 453 nm band overlapped with that of 267 nm band, and the uncertainty in the resolution of the 267 nm band was much more than the variation in half-band width. The decrease in the intensity of the absorption band with the increase in temperature may be due to the change in band shape (λ slightly increased) and/or decrease in concentration (however small it may be) of the system.

On the addition of β -cyclodextrin, the absorbance of APB increased and the increase depends on the concentration of β -cyclodextrin. It may be noted here that even though the absorbance of APB- β -cyclodextrin systems is higher than that of APB, the increase in absorbance is not very much. In the presence of β -cyclodextrin the absorbance maximum of APB (i.e. 453 nm band) slightly shifted to higher wavelength (456 nm). Our attempts to measure the shift in λ_{max} with the increasing addition of β -cyclodextrin were not successful. From the difference between the absorbances of APB with and without β -cyclodextrin, a new band could be detected at 472 nm which could be attributed to the cyclodextrin-APB (host-guest) complex. In addition, isosbestic points were observed at 430 and 360 nm. So, the presence of isosbestic points as well as the appearance of a new band indicate that there is an equilibrium between the complexed β -cyclodextrin and free APB. It may be noted that as the temperature of the solution of APB- β -cyclodextrin is increased from 298 to 308 K, ϵ_{iso} decreased from 21969

to 21002 $\text{dm}^3 \text{ mol}^{-1} \text{ cm}^{-1}$ (even though λ_{iso} practically remained unaltered). Here it should be worth mentioning that one should be very careful in interpreting the experimental results, in which the temperature (or solvent composition-dielectric constant of the medium) is varied¹⁹. Such changes, in general, affect not only the relative concentrations of the absorbing species but also the shapes of the absorption bands of the individual components. From the present data, it appears that the slight decrease in ϵ_{iso} may be due to the decrease in concentration of the complex. Our attempts to obtain the information of the shape of the bands were not successful due to experimental difficulties and the small decrease did not cause any noticeable change in the isosbestic point. Kortum²⁰ had also noticed that at higher concentration of dioxane in dioxane-iodine system, the λ_{iso} shifted considerably.

The absorbance of APB- β -cyclodextrin (excess) is higher than that of APB, particularly between 420 and 523 nm and the differences is maximum at 478 nm, i.e. at highest concentration of β -cyclodextrin (≈ 100 times) the λ_{CT} shifted from 472 to 478 nm. The shift may be due to altered dielectric constant of the medium and this in turn may lower the ground/excited state of the complex, and this may cause the transition energies to vary. The λ_{iso} , at higher concentration of β -cyclodextrin has shifted from 430 nm to 418 (blue shifts) and the existing model is not in a position to explain this shift. The equilibrium constant obtained using Nagakura's procedure is higher than that obtained using Benesi-Hildebrand equation, and we are not in a position to explain this. However the trend, the decrease in the value of K with the increase in temperature is the same. The molar extinction coefficient obtained by separating K_{CD} and ϵ_{CD} from $K_{\text{CD}}\epsilon_{\text{CD}}$ is low. However, it may be noted that when excess of β -cyclodextrin is added to a solution of APB of $\sim 3.2 \times 10^{-1} \text{ M}$, the increase in absorbance is ≈ 0.18 and large amount of APB remains uncomplexed. So, it is evident that APB is not able to interact with β -cyclodextrin strongly (i.e. probably, APB may be due to its size, is not able to fit into the cavity of β -cyclodextrin properly and hence the interaction may be weak).

APB- α -cyclodextrin complex :

On the addition of α -cyclodextrin, the absorbance of APB slightly increases and this increase in absorbance depends on the concentration of α -cyclodextrin. Here it may be noted that even though the absorbance of APB- α -cyclodextrin increases, the increase in absorbance of APB is relatively low compared to that caused by the addition of β -cyclodextrin of the same strength (to the same amount of APB). So it may be inferred that the relative strength of α -CD and APB

interaction is much lower than that of β -CD and APB. In the presence of α -cyclodextrin, the absorption maxima of APB slightly shifts to high wavelength (455 nm) and at very high concentration, the λ_{\max} of APB is found to be ~ 465 nm. This shift may be due to the change in dielectric constant of the medium.

The increase in absorbance of APB with the addition of α -cyclodextrin, can be attributed to the formation of a new species. From the differences in absorbances of APB with and without α -cyclodextrin, a new band with absorption maximum at ≈ 492 nm was obtained. However, as the differences of absorbances are very small, the uncertainty in the measurement of λ_{CT} is relatively large. An isosbestic point was located at ~ 432 nm ($\epsilon_{\text{iso}} = 24604 \pm 117 \text{ dm}^3 \text{ mol}^{-1} \text{ cm}^{-1}$). In the case of β -cyclodextrin-APB, there were two isosbestic points at 430 and 360 nm whereas in the present case there is only one and we are not in a position to comment on this. The presence of isosbestic point and the appearance of a new band indicate the formation of a molecular adduct, formed between α -cyclodextrin and APB. Our attempts to determine the half-width of the band λ_{iso} , were not successful (due to the uncertainty, in the determination of λ , which was higher than the change in $\lambda_{1/2}$). At very high concentration, λ_{iso} was observed at ~ 470 nm. It may be noted that such observation (i.e. shift in λ_{iso}) has been reported²⁰. It may also be noted that in the case of β -cyclodextrin under the same condition (i.e. in the presence of excess β -cyclodextrin), the λ_{iso} appeared at 420 nm which is difficult to explain on the basis of available models. As in the case of β -cyclodextrin-APB complex, the absorbance of the complex increases linearly with the increase in concentration of β -cyclodextrin. However, at very high concentration of α -cyclodextrin (excess), the absorbance was much lower than expected and we feel that this may be due to the formation of higher order complex. The equilibrium constant for the formation of the complex at various temperatures were determined and the results are summarised in Table 2. However, it is surprising to note that the equilibrium constant of α -cyclodextrin-APB was much lower than that of APB and β -cyclodextrin, whereas the molar extinction constant, ϵ_{CT} was higher than that corresponds to β -cyclodextrin complex. The numerical value of ϵ_{CT} of α -cyclodextrin-APB indicates that the complexes are weak²¹.

The equilibrium constants were also calculated by the procedure described by Nagakura¹¹ and the value, as in the case of β -cyclodextrin-APB, is slightly higher, but the trend is similar. As it is mentioned earlier, in cases where B-H method is used, the uncertainty in the K and ϵ (obtained by separating K and ϵ from $K\epsilon$) are quite large. However, in

the procedure developed by Nagakura one obtains the value of K directly, and these values are more acceptable (rather than obtained by separating K and ϵ from $K\epsilon$). The ΔG° values of α -cyclodextrin-APB and of β -cyclodextrin-APB are nearly the same ($\sim 7 \text{ kJ mol}^{-1}$); ΔH° in the former case ($16.63 \text{ kJ mol}^{-1}$) is higher compared to the latter case ($12.47 \text{ kJ mol}^{-1}$). Similar observations were reported by Lewis and Hansen⁷ for some cyclodextrin complexes. However, the entropy value of α -cyclodextrin-APB is slightly higher than that of β -cyclodextrin-APB. As the enthalpy values in both the cases are small, we are tempted to infer that the host-guest complex formation of cyclodextrins-APB is enthalpy-controlled rather than entropy-controlled.

The 'stability' of the complex is usually referred with respect to the magnitude of ΔG° and hence to K . A host is considered to be a good host if it forms a strong complex with large K value. So, on the basis of K value, one can infer that β -cyclodextrin is a better host compared to α -cyclodextrin ($K_{\alpha\text{-cyclodextrin-APB}} = 752$, $K_{\beta\text{-cyclodextrin-APB}} = 1206 \text{ dm}^3 \text{ mol}^{-1} \text{ cm}^{-1}$ at 298 K). However, ΔH° is generally closely related to stabilisation by charge transfer forces and the concept of strength is based on them¹⁶. As the complex (in the case of β -cyclodextrin-APB) becomes more stable, ΔH° becomes more negative. The decrease in entropy due to the loss of freedom (as host and guest combine to form complex) also tends to become larger (compared to α -cyclodextrin-APB). It is reported in the literature that $-\Delta S^\circ$ is a linear function of ΔH° ²². However, Rekharsky and Inoue²³ showed that there is no scientific basis to expect such a correlation. These two functions have opposite effects on the value of ΔG° . As the charge transfer resonance interactions cause ΔH° to become more negative, the corresponding decrease in entropy prevents ΔG° from becoming negative as rapidly as does ΔH° . However, it may be mentioned that as values of ΔS° in the present case are too small, we feel that the host-guest complexation as in other cases is enthalpy-controlled rather than entropy-controlled.

Azurene-A- β -cyclodextrin complexes :

Azurene-A has absorption bands at 243 ± 2 ($\epsilon \approx 9600 \pm 152$), 288 ± 1 ($\epsilon \approx 24035 \pm 131$) and 632 ± 1 nm ($\epsilon \approx 31458 \pm 148 \text{ dm}^3 \text{ mol}^{-1} \text{ cm}^{-1}$) (lit.²⁴ λ_{\max} 632 nm, ϵ_{\max} $3350 \text{ dm}^3 \text{ mol}^{-1} \text{ cm}^{-1}$). In addition, a shoulder appears at ~ 320 nm. The 632 nm band can be ascribed to the π - π^* transition. (Due to extended conjugation, the π - π^* transition band has undergone considerable red-shift). The molar extinction coefficient of 632 nm band was determined using several solutions of different concentrations and it was noticed that when the concentration of azurene-A was higher than 10^{-4} M , the molar extinction coefficient slightly in-

creased whereas the λ_{\max} remained the same. (However, in our experiments, the concentration of azu-A was kept very low, 2×10^{-6} M). With the increase in temperature from 298 to 308 K, the molar extinction coefficient decreased from 31485 to 30142 $\text{dm}^3 \text{mol}^{-1} \text{cm}^{-1}$, whereas the half-width of 632 nm band increased from 2383 to 2432 ± 14 cm^{-1} . Our attempts to measure the half-widths of other two bands were not successful due to the large uncertainties.

With the addition of β -cyclodextrin, the intensities of all the bands increased, but the increase in intensity of 632 nm is much more compared to other two bands. At higher concentration of β -cyclodextrin, the apparent λ_{\max} slightly shifted to higher wavelength (~ 4 nm) and the shift remained the same even at the saturation concentration of β -cyclodextrin. From the differences in the absorption of free azurene and complexed azurene, a new band, centred at ~ 639 nm was detected. An isosbestic point was observed at 611 nm. The presence of an isosbestic point and the appearance of a new band whose intensity is reversible with the reversion of temperature indicate that azurene-A interacts with β -cyclodextrin to form a reversible host-guest complex.

The increase in absorbance of 632 nm band was from 0.6563 to 0.7405 when the concentrations of β -cyclodextrin was increased from 3.3×10^{-4} to 3.18×10^{-3} M. This indicates that the concentration of the complex formed is very low or the molar extinction coefficient of the complex is low. It is interesting to note that when excess of β -cyclodextrin was added, the isosbestic point shifted from 611 to ~ 614 nm ($\epsilon_{\text{iso}} \cong 28072 \text{ dm}^3 \text{ mol}^{-1} \text{ cm}^{-1}$) and 288 nm band had a blue-shift of ~ 5 nm. In addition, there is an enhancement of absorption in this range. The absorption at lower wavelengths has increased considerably and from the difference in absorbance of azurene-A with and without β -cyclodextrin, we could locate another new band at ~ 337 nm and under such conditions another isosbestic point was located at ~ 306 nm. It may be mentioned that as this band appeared only at very high concentrations of β -cyclodextrin, it was not possible to determine stoichiometry, and hence the equilibrium constant and molar extinction coefficient of the complex using this band. Azurene-A is an electron-rich compound. The size of the parent molecule of azurene-A seems to be larger than the cavity of β -cyclodextrin. The substitution on the side-chain causes slight deviation from planarity of the molecule. So, we feel that azurene-A is not able to be accommodated/fitted into the cavity of β -cyclodextrin and as the molecule is not completely planar the interaction (hydrophobic) between azurene-A and β -cyclodextrin is expected to be weak. The equilibrium constant and other thermodynamic parameters of these com-

plexes are given in Table 1. From the low value of ΔH° and small positive value of ΔS° , it is not possible to infer whether the process is enthalpy-controlled or entropy-controlled.

Azurene-B- β -cyclodextrin complex :

The electronic spectra of azurene-B is similar to that of azurene-A. Azurene-B has absorption maxima at 646 ± 1 ($\epsilon = 42600 \pm 132$), 290 ± 1 ($\epsilon = 31427 \pm 143$) and 245 ± 1 nm ($\epsilon = 13820 \pm 122 \text{ dm}^3 \text{ mol}^{-1} \text{ cm}^{-1}$). In addition, a shoulder appeared at ~ 320 nm. The 646 nm band, is due to the extended conjugation of the π - π^* transition. The slight red-shift of all these bands (compared to azurene-A) may be due to the presence of two more CH_3 groups. Concentration independence of ϵ and λ indicates that the azurene-B has not dimerised (with the increase in concentration) within the experimental range of concentrations of the dye (10^{-6} to 10^{-5} M). With the increase in temperature of the system from 298 to 308 K, the molar extinction coefficient slightly decreased (from 42600 to $41675 \text{ dm}^3 \text{ mol}^{-1} \text{ cm}^{-1}$) and the half-band width of 646 nm band increased from 2271 to 2330 cm^{-1} .

On addition of β -cyclodextrin, the absorbance of azurene-B increased and the enhancement of the absorbance at 646 nm was maximum. From the differences in absorption of azurene-B with and without β -cyclodextrin, we could locate a new band at 658 ± 1 nm and an isosbestic point at 629 ± 1 nm ($\epsilon_{\text{iso}} = 39447 \pm 113 \text{ dm}^3 \text{ mol}^{-1} \text{ cm}^{-1}$). The 658 nm band appeared at slightly higher wavelength (~ 4 nm) when the concentration of β -cyclodextrin was increased from $\sim 2 \times 10^{-5}$ to 3×10^{-3} M. When the excess β -cyclodextrin was added, a new band at ~ 332 nm appeared and an isosbestic point was observed at 530 nm ($\epsilon_{\text{iso}} = 5235 \pm 123 \text{ dm}^3 \text{ mol}^{-1} \text{ cm}^{-1}$). The appearance of a new band (i.e. 658 nm) with the addition of β -cyclodextrin whose absorbance is reversible with the reversal of temperature, and the presence of an isosbestic point, indicate that azurene-B interacts with β -cyclodextrin forming azurene- β -cyclodextrin complex.

The equilibrium constant for the interaction of azurene-B with β -cyclodextrin calculated using the B-H equation (where concentration of donor should be much higher compared the acceptor) and the one calculated using Nagakura's equation (which is obtained by solving simultaneous equations) agree very well (Table 1). The enthalpy and entropy values of the complex indicate that the interaction between azurene-B and β -cyclodextrin is weak. The strength of interaction depends upon the nature/type of molecules. Azurene-B is cationic dye, but it has π - as well as non-bonded electrons and is generally considered as an electron-rich compound, i.e. as a donor rather than an acceptor of

electron. It can be easily visualised that β -cyclodextrin can act as electron donor. So, as both are electron-rich molecules, naturally the interaction between azurene-B and β -cyclodextrin, as in the case of azurene-A- β -cyclodextrin, is weak. In addition, the azurene-B is a bigger molecule and the substitution of CH_3 groups on the molecule causes deviation in the planar structure. Therefore, the higher electron density, larger size and deviation from planarity of azurene-B makes it difficult to interact with β -cyclodextrin and this is reflected on its spectroscopic and thermodynamic parameters. Even though the free energy and enthalpy of complexation is negative, the values are small. These small values of ΔH° indicate that the complex is not expected to be enthalpy-controlled. Even though the entropy of the complex is positive, the value is very small ($\sim 3 \text{ J mol}^{-1}$). Therefore, it is not possible to say whether the complexation is enthalpy-controlled or entropy-controlled.

Azurene-C- β -cyclodextrin complexes :

Azurene-C has absorption maxima at 612 ± 1 ($\epsilon = 33024 \pm 135$), 285 ± 1 ($\epsilon = 24611 \pm 127$) and $241 \pm 1 \text{ nm}$ ($\epsilon = 8472 \pm 85 \text{ dm}^3 \text{ mol}^{-1} \text{ cm}^{-1}$), in addition to a shoulder at $\sim 320 \text{ nm}$. The concentration-independence of ϵ and λ indicates that in the experimental range of concentration, as in other cases, azurene-C is in the monomeric form. The molar extinction coefficient of azurene-C decreases (from 33024 to $31900 \text{ dm}^3 \text{ mol}^{-1} \text{ cm}^{-1}$) with the increase in temperature from 298 to 318, whereas the half-width of the band (e.g. $\nu_{1/2}$ of 612 nm) increases from 2107 to 2188 cm^{-1} .

On the addition of β -cyclodextrin, the absorbance of azurene-C increases. From the differences between the absorption of azurene-C with and without β -cyclodextrin, we could locate a new band at $\sim 622 \text{ nm}$ and an isosbestic point at $\sim 650 \text{ nm}$. However, when excess of β -cyclodextrin was added to the same concentration of azurene-C, a new band (as in the case of azurene-A and azurene-B- β -cyclodextrin), appears $\sim 330 \text{ nm}$ which could not be characterised. The presence of a new band (622 nm) in addition to the appearance of λ_{iso} indicates that azurene-C interacts with β -cyclodextrin giving rise to a host-guest complex which has an absorption maximum at 622 nm. Our attempts to study the effects of temperature on λ_{iso} and ϵ_{iso} were not successful as the observed variations were within the experimental error-limits. The equilibrium constant and other thermodynamic parameters for the complexation are summarised in Table 1. The equilibrium constant at 298 K is $1862 \pm 134 \text{ dm}^3 \text{ mol}^{-1} \text{ cm}^{-1}$ which is reasonable. However, it is difficult to reason the relatively low value of molar extinction coefficient of the complex, as generally the strong complexes (larger values of K , ΔH° and ΔG°) have larger values of ϵ .

Here it may be noted that the molar extinction coefficient depends on the change in dipole moment/transition probability of the electron from highest occupied orbital of the donor to the lowest unoccupied orbital of acceptor. The enthalpy and free energy are negative, and entropy change is small and positive. So, the stability of the complex may arise due to the contribution of negative enthalpy and positive entropy.

When one compares the spectroscopic and thermodynamic properties of azurene- β -cyclodextrin complexes, one feels that amongst the three complexes, azurene-C seems to form strongest complex with β -cyclodextrin. Even though all the three azures that we have studied, have the same basic (skeleton) structures, the substitutions are different. Azurene-B has three CH_3 groups and this may cause more deviation from the planar structure of the molecule. For the complex formation, the ideal situation is, when the guest molecule is encapsulated into the host system, which in turn mainly depends on the size and structure of the guest/host system. As azures are big molecules having different substitutions, they may not be able to be accommodated in the cavity of cyclodextrins. The interaction between azurene-C with β -cyclodextrin is expected to be the strongest compared to the other azures and β -cyclodextrin. From our experimental findings (thermodynamic data), we notice that the interaction between β -cyclodextrin and azures are weak, and they vary in the order : azurene-C- β -cyclodextrin > azurene-A- β -cyclodextrin > azurene-B- β -cyclodextrin. From the values of enthalpy and entropy, it is not possible to emphasise whether the processes are enthalpy-controlled or entropy-controlled.

Azures- α -cyclodextrin complexes :

With the addition of α -cyclodextrin, the absorptions of azures increase, but the increase in absorbance is marginal and this indicates that the interaction between α -cyclodextrin and azures is very weak. From the differences between the absorbances of azurene-A, azurene-B and azurene-C with and without α -cyclodextrin, we could detect the presence of molecular adduct bands at $\sim 632 \pm 2$, 652 ± 2 and $\sim 620 \pm 2 \text{ nm}$, respectively. In addition, there is enhancement in absorption between 260 and 340 nm, with absorption maxima at 290 nm. Our attempts to characterise the charge transfer bands (e.g. ϵ , $\nu_{1/2}$ etc.) and to determine the equilibrium constants for complex formation by increasing the concentration of α -cyclodextrin, were not successful (the base line of the spectra itself shifts to higher value) due to the low solubility of α -cyclodextrin and its complex. The increase in absorbances of azures- α -cyclodextrin is relatively very small compared to those due to azures- β -

cyclodextrin. From the experimental data, it is clear that interaction between α -cyclodextrin and azarenes is very weak compared to that between β -cyclodextrin and azarenes, which may be due to the differences in the size of the cavities of cyclodextrins.

From the present investigation, it is evident that α - and β -cyclodextrins form host-guest complexes with phenolphthalein, acridine, APB and azarenes. The interaction between the hosts and guests is weak, β -cyclodextrin forms relatively stronger complexes with the above dyes.

Experimental

Stock solutions of dyes (guest) were prepared ($\sim 10^{-4}$ M) by weighting appropriate amount and dissolving the same in double-distilled water. Further dilution was made ($\sim 10^{-5}$ M) for recording the electronic absorption spectra. Required amount of solid samples of the hosts (cyclodextrins) was added to solution (10 ml) of the guests (dyes), so that the final concentration of the host (with a fixed concentration of the guests-dyes) was $\sim 10^{-4}$ to 10^{-2} M. The spectra of the dyes with and without the hosts were recorded with a Hitachi-330-NIR-UV-VIS and Beckman DU-650 spectrophotometers fitted with matched pair of cells of 1 cm optical path-length placed in a thermostated cell holder. Constant temperature ($\pm 0.1^\circ$) was maintained by circulating water of constant temperature around the cell holder using a thermostat MLW-Flussing keits. For the sake of brevity, only two typical spectra are included. Equilibrium constants were determined using modified Benesi-Hildebrand¹⁰ equation and Nagakura's¹¹ procedure. On the addition of host, the absorbance of guest molecules decreased and the decrease in absorbance depended on the concentration of the host. By knowing the stoichiometry of the complex, (Job's method) and presuming that the decrease in absorbance of the guest is due to the non-absorbance of the guest which has complexed with the host, the concentration of the complex and hence the equilibrium constant for the complex formation could be calculated. The thermodynamic parameters for the complexation were calculated using the standard procedures.

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